

THE HISTORY OF THE TASHKENT WOMEN'S EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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ABSTRACT

This educational institution was established in 1919 in the Shaykhantahur district of Tashkent, in the former residence of Solikhujaboy, and was specially organized for Uzbek women. However, despite this, one of the major challenges faced by the institution was the limited number of students.

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The institution was designed to accommodate a total of 200 indigenous women. The establishment opened on October 1. In order to allow Uzbek girls from remote areas to arrive, the admission period was set until October 15. Until this date, applications from representatives of other nationalities were postponed; they were admitted only if a sufficient number of applications from girls of the indigenous population had not been received by October 15¹. However, in the first year, apart from 30 students from Old Tashkent, no other applicants sought admission to the institution. Due to the insufficient number of girls from the indigenous population, 30–40 Tatar girls were also admitted as students. The increase in the number of female students at the institution was achieved with the assistance of regional departments of public education.

Initially, the activities of the educational institution were limited to literacy and basic arithmetic instruction. According to the officials, all of the girls were illiterate, and overcoming this issue was considered an urgent task. During the 1921–1922 academic year,

¹ Usmon. O'zbek qizi, bilim yurtiga! / Qizil bayroq. 1921, № 94.

this process did not yield satisfactory results. Over this period, eight administrators were replaced at the institution.

In 1922, it was decided to change the name of this educational establishment, and it came to be known as a “*Bilim Yurti*” (educational institution). From that year onward, the new leadership appointed to the institution began to properly organize educational activities. In the same year, admission requirements were expanded, seating facilities were provided, efforts were initiated to establish a library, and a theatre club was organized². In some sources, it is recorded that the number of female students at the educational institution reached 200 in 1922.³ An examination of the early activities of the *Bilim Yurti* indicates that without effectively establishing primary education among indigenous women, the secondary specialized stage of education could not achieve the intended results.

At the same time, social factors also exerted a significant influence on the life of the institution. For example, one of the first graduates of the institution was Tojikhon Rustambekova. Her father, Rustambek Domla, was a teacher in the new-method schools and therefore did not oppose his daughter’s education in a Russian school. However, even appearing in public while wearing the *paranji* was considered alarming. One could face public condemnation and even stone-throwing merely because of rumors such as, “So-and-so’s daughter is studying in a Russian school.”

Despite the risk of such difficulties, in 1923 seven girls graduated from the institution: Robiya Nosirova, Manzura Sobirqoriyeva (Oydin), Hamida Tojiyeva, Manzura Yangulotova, Sharifa Shorahmedova, Nazmi Ma’zumova, and Tojikhon Rustambekova. They were awarded gold medals, with their names inscribed on one side and the phrase “bearers of the light of enlightenment to a benighted people” engraved on the other⁴. This suggests that the *Bilim Yurti* primarily emphasized ideological propaganda. Only a very small proportion of those admitted to the institution successfully completed their studies.

Several reasons and factors may be identified to explain this situation. An article published in *Ishtirokyun* describes the issue as follows: “Although the admission of Turkestanian women—who had lived their lives without exposure to knowledge and enlightenment and without entering the broader world—into the women’s teacher training institute (*dorulmuallimot*) is a joyful development, upon observing its shortcomings, our joy regarding our Turkestanian sisters has proved to be nothing more than an illusion.”

This situation was reflected in a number of problems, including the deplorable condition of the girls’ dormitory, the inability of teachers and girls from the indigenous population to understand one another, difficulties in interpersonal relations, and the teachers’ failure to become familiar with the students’ cultural and personal characteristics⁵.

Nevertheless, gradual progress was observed in the activities of the *Bilim Yurti* from year to year. In 1923, a Komsomol⁶ organization was established at the institution. Sobira

² За пять лет сборник по вопросам работы коммунистической партии среди женщин Средней Азии. – Москва: Центральное издательство народов СССР. 1925. – 74-стр.

³ R.U. Turkiston xotin-qizlari o’rtasida nima ishlandi / Turkiston. 1923, November 16.

⁴ UzMA. F. R-2854, op. 1, d. 17, l. 2-3.

⁵ Toshkentlik Miromon / Ishtirokyun. 1919, № 93.

⁶ **Komsomol** is the Russian abbreviation for the All-Union Leninist Young Communist League (VLKSM), an organization established for youth during the Soviet period. Its members consisted of young people between the ages of 14 and 28.

Kholdorova served as its secretary, and in 1924 the institution was elevated to the status of a regional educational establishment and was renamed the “Uzbek Women’s Educational Institution”⁷. A number of specialists in the field of medicine also emerged from this institution. Among them were Nasiba Abdullayeva, Khasana Yunusova, Munira Tursunkhojayeva, Nazokat Orifkhanova, and Manzura Yangulatova.

The duration of study at the *Bilim Yurti* was four years, consisting of two preparatory and two main classes. Graduates of literacy schools were also admitted to the preparatory classes and, within four years, obtained a teaching diploma. The institution primarily enrolled girls and young women who had experienced conflict with their parents, had been forced into marriage, had suffered abuse from their brothers, or had been subjected to mistreatment by their husbands.⁸ From this information, an important social aspect can be identified: the *Bilim Yurti* functioned not only as an educational institution but also as a “shelter” for women.

In addition to the main academic activities, political, sewing, literary, and other extracurricular circles operated at the institution. Among the girls who received education in the literary circle were individuals who later became some of the early writers of the Soviet period, including poets, authors, and journalists. These included the journalist Sobira Kholdorova, the writer Oydin Sobirova, and the poet Khosiyat Tillakhanova. They were cadres imbued with Soviet ideology. Consequently, in their works they emphasized themes of liberation and freedom granted by the Bolsheviks and later expressed support for the Party’s *Hujum* campaigns.

In conclusion, although the first women’s educational institution established in Tashkent was formally designated as a secondary specialized educational establishment, in practice it did not fully meet these requirements. This was due to the various challenges faced by the institution. As a result, it became not merely a place of learning, but a center for promoting and embodying the government’s policy toward women.

The organization served as the principal body responsible for implementing the directives of the Communist Party (Kopartiya) among the youth.

⁷ UzMA. F. R-2854, op. 1, d. 17, l. 2-3.

⁸ UzMA. F. R-2854, op. 1, d. 17, l. 1.